

A Sufficient Condition for Asymptotic Stability in a Modified Fowler Model and Seashell Pattern Reconstruction Using PINNs

Jingkai Wang*

Abstract

We investigate seashell pattern formation through an activator-inhibitor system, focusing particularly on a modified Fowler model. The modification in the activator dynamics preserves the biological mechanisms while enhancing the tractability for stability analysis. The finite element scheme is developed to solve the system numerically on irregular seashell surfaces. We propose two key theorems: the first demonstrates a sufficient condition on the parameters for the existence of a stable fixed point using Turing instability analysis; the second derives an amplification matrix that characterizes the stability region of the finite element scheme. The parameter conditions for the existence of a Hopf bifurcation in the modified Fowler model without diffusion are derived and verified. Given parameters satisfying the sufficient condition for asymptotic stability, numerical simulations confirm the convergence behavior of the dynamical system over time. We explore the inverse parameter identification using physics-informed neural networks (PINNs), capturing the overall seashell patterns effectively.

Keywords: seashell patterns, Fowler model, finite element method, variational formulation, Turing instability analysis, Hopf bifurcation, stability region, physics-informed neural networks

1 Introduction

The pigmentation of seashells manifests complex and heterogeneous spatial patterns, deriving from the biochemical effects along the growth edge. To understand the development of seashell patterns, reaction-diffusion models such as activator-inhibitor systems have been proposed [7]. The activator-inhibitor system model introduces two interacting dynamical systems: the first captures the activator that facilitates the growth of spatial patterns, while the second system denotes the inhibitor that suppresses the activator development. Two activator-inhibitor system models employed in seashell pattern studies are the Gierer–Meinhardt model and a modified Fowler model. Comparing to the Fowler model [6], the modified version in our work reconstructs the nonlinear term of the activator dynamics to preserve biological meanings and improve the tractability for stability analysis. While the Gierer–Meinhardt model is effective in capturing the activator-inhibitor dynamics in seashell patterns, the modified Fowler model achieves more realistic pattern simulations by introducing the global regulatory effects. A wide range of studies has applied the finite element methods (FEM) and other numerical methods on the reaction-diffusion model [3, 10, 26]. The stability condition for the reduced Gierer–Meinhardt (GM) model has been introduced, where the fixed point can be derived analytically [2]. The physics-informed neural networks have been proposed as a framework for solving inverse problems, including the identification of parameters and initial conditions of partial differential equations (PDE) [21].

*Department of Applied Physics and Applied Mathematics, Columbia University (jw4673@columbia.edu)

In our work, we leverage finite element methods to derive the numerical results of the 2-dimensional activator-inhibitor systems. After the variational formulation, the non-linear system is discretized using a time-stepping scheme such as a semi-implicit scheme [17, 18]. Since the activator-inhibitor system captures the interaction behaviors, the numerical solution is updated at each time step until convergence. Two key theorems are proposed. Theorem 1 is derived from the Turing instability analysis, yielding a sufficient condition to analyze the convergence behavior of the activator-inhibitor system. Although the fixed point cannot be computed in closed form and may not exist in general, the sufficient condition for its existence and stability is derived analytically. Theorem 4 derived an amplification matrix based on Theorem 1 to capture the stability region of the finite element scheme. We have rigorously analyzed the Hopf bifurcation conditions by deriving the parameter threshold and associated inequalities in Theorem 2 and Theorem 3. We implement the numerical methods on the irregular seashell shape using the parameters that satisfy the sufficient condition. The physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) are introduced to identify the parameters from the real seashell image.

Figure 1: A image of seashell patterns.

2 Activator Inhibitor Systems for Seashell Pattern Modeling

As a subclass of reaction-diffusion models, the activator-inhibitor system is leveraged to measure the evolution of spatial patterns over time [11]. A real image of seashell patterns is displayed in Figure 1. Here, $u(x, y, t)$ denotes the density of the activator that promotes pattern formation, while $v(x, y, t)$ denotes the inhibitor concentration responsible for suppressing the activator population. At each time step, the distribution of u is employed to represent the pigment intensity reflecting the surface patterns of seashells. The Gierer-Meinhardt model and the modified Fowler model are introduced and analyzed.

2.1 Model Utilization

The Gierer-Meinhardt (GM) Model [7] measures the biomedical interaction between activator and inhibitor using the following formula:

$$\partial_t u = D_u \nabla^2 u + \rho \left(\frac{u^2}{v(1 + \kappa u^2)} - \mu u \right), \quad (1)$$

$$\partial_t v = D_v \nabla^2 v + \rho(u^2 - k_u v), \quad (2)$$

where $D_u, D_v, \rho, \kappa, \mu > 0$. In the formula, parameter ρ captures the speed of reaction kinetics between activator and inhibitor; κ represents the saturation constant that modulates the growth of the activator; μ is the activator decay rate and k_u is the inhibitor decay rate. In the diffusion term, parameters D_u and D_v represent spatial diffusion rates of the activator and inhibitor respectively. Homogeneous solutions appear when the activator diffuses rapidly (large D_u); while the imbalance pattern formulation due to Turing instability becomes prominent when the inhibitor exhibits a higher diffusion rate (large D_v). The emergence of biological patterns is determined by the parameters that reflect the reaction, diffusion and interaction behaviors, along with the initial state.

The Fowler model [6] is motivated by the Gierer-Meinhardt model by retaining activator-inhibitor dynamics, while the activator-inhibitor system model leverages more parameters to prevent unbounded growth and enhance robustness. In this work, we introduce a modified Fowler model where the reaction term in the activator dynamics is reformulated. The modification preserves the biological mechanisms of the activator-inhibitor system while suppressing the strength of the non-linear feedback. Among new parameters, ρ_0 controls the activator growth by dampening the nonlinear feedback, σ prevents the inhibitor concentration from collapsing to zero level; h_0 is leveraged to prevent singular behavior. The modified Fowler model is written as

$$\partial_t u = D_u \nabla^2 u + \frac{\rho}{(v + h_0)(1 + \kappa u^2 + \rho_0)} u^2 - \mu_2 u, \quad (3)$$

$$\partial_t v = D_v \nabla^2 v + \sigma + \rho \frac{u^2}{1 + \kappa u^2} - \eta v, \quad (4)$$

where $D_u, D_v, \mu_2, \eta, \sigma, \rho, \rho_0, \kappa, h_0 > 0$. Both the Gierer-Meinhardt model and the modified Fowler model are used to capture the variation of pigmentation patterns of seashells at each time step by measuring the biological interaction between activator and inhibitor. In certain boundaries, the activator and inhibitor demonstrate time-dependent dynamics, formulated by the equations, providing the spatial patterns. The finite element method (FEM) with triangular discretizations is leveraged to reduce the IBVP problem into a system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs), which can be evolved in time using implicit schemes. Specifically, when parameters ρ, σ, h_0 are set to be zero, the modified Fowler model is reduced to the Gierer-Meinhardt model.

2.2 A Sufficient Condition for Stable Fixed Point

As shown in [2], a stability condition was derived for a reduced Gierer-Meinhardt model. However, the modified Fowler model is more intricate since the fixed point cannot be computed analytically. To analyze the stability of fixed points in the activator-inhibitor system of the modified Fowler model, we consider the following system without the diffusion term.

$$\partial_t u = \frac{\rho u^2}{(v + h_0)(1 + \kappa u^2 + \rho_0)} - \mu_2 u, \quad (5)$$

$$\partial_t v = \sigma + \rho \frac{u^2}{1 + \kappa u^2} - \eta v. \quad (6)$$

The fixed point (u^*, v^*) for the above non-linear system satisfies the following equations that

$$\rho u^* = \mu_2 (v^* + h_0) (1 + \kappa u^{*2} + \rho_0) \quad (7)$$

$$v^* = \frac{1}{\eta} \left(\sigma + \rho \frac{u^{*2}}{1 + \kappa u^{*2}} \right) \quad (8)$$

By replacing the formula of v^* , it can be computed that u^* should satisfy the equation that

$$f(u^*) = \frac{\mu_2}{u^*} \left(\frac{1}{\eta} \left(\sigma + \rho \cdot \frac{u^{*2}}{1 + \kappa u^{*2}} \right) + h_0 \right) \cdot (1 + \kappa u^{*2} + \rho_0) - \rho = 0. \quad (9)$$

And the Jacobian matrix at the fixed point can be derived as

$$J(u^*, v^*) = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_2 \left(\frac{2(1 + \rho_0)}{1 + \kappa(u^*)^2 + \rho_0} - 1 \right) & -\frac{\mu_2 u^*}{v^* + h_0} \\ \frac{2\rho u^*}{(1 + \kappa(u^*)^2)^2} & -\eta \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

To study the Turing instability, we analyze the behaviors of spatial perturbations evolving around the steady state at (u^*, v^*) . Suppose D is the diffusion matrix and $d = D_u/D_v$, and then the Jacobian matrix is modified by incorporating the effect of diffusion with $J_k = J - k^2 D$:

$$J_k = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_2 \left(\frac{2(1 + \rho_0)}{1 + \kappa(u^*)^2 + \rho_0} - 1 \right) - dk^2 & -\frac{\mu_2 u^*}{v^* + h_0} \\ \frac{2\rho u^*}{(1 + \kappa(u^*)^2)^2} & -\eta - k^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad D = \begin{bmatrix} d & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

Since the stability of the fixed points requires the real part of all eigenvalues to be negative, this condition is equivalent to ensuring that $\text{Tr}(J_k) < 0$ and $\text{Det}(J_k) > 0$ for non-negative integer k .

$$\text{Tr}(J_k) = \mu_2 \left(\frac{2(1 + \rho_0)}{1 + \kappa(u^*)^2 + \rho_0} - 1 \right) - \eta - (d + 1)k^2 < 0, \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Det}(J_k) = \left[\mu_2 \left(\frac{2(1 + \rho_0)}{1 + \kappa(u^*)^2 + \rho_0} - 1 \right) - dk^2 \right] \cdot (-\eta - k^2) + \left(\frac{\mu_2 u^*}{v^* + h_0} \cdot \frac{2\rho u^*}{(1 + \kappa(u^*)^2)^2} \right) > 0. \quad (13)$$

One sufficient condition to ensure the inequalities is requiring $u^* > \sqrt{\frac{1+\rho_0}{\kappa}}$. From Equation (9), we observe that $f(u^*) \rightarrow \infty$ as $u^* \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, if $f(\sqrt{\frac{1+\rho_0}{\kappa}}) < 0$, by the Intermediate Value Theorem, there exists at least one fixed point satisfying $u^* > \sqrt{\frac{1+\rho_0}{\kappa}}$. Then Theorem 1 can be derived to demonstrate the sufficient condition.

Theorem 1. *There exists a fixed point (u^*, v^*) , and the fixed point is stable if the following condition holds, where*

$$0 < \mu_2 < \frac{\rho \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1 + \rho_0}{\kappa}}}{(2 + 2\rho_0) \left(\frac{1}{\eta} \left(\sigma + \frac{\rho(1 + \rho_0)}{\kappa(2 + \rho_0)} \right) + h_0 \right)}. \quad (14)$$

Moreover, if the sufficient condition holds, there exists a fixed point that is asymptotically stable. In the small neighborhood of the fixed point (u^*, v^*) , the activator concentration and inhibitor concentration converge to it over time.

2.3 Hopf Bifurcation Analysis

The occurrence of Hopf bifurcation in reaction-diffusion systems is widely analyzed [15, 23]. The Hopf bifurcation condition for the modified Fowler model is analyzed based on the reaction terms of the system. Then the Hopf bifurcation occurs when a pair of complex conjugate eigenvalues cross the imaginary axis, i.e. $\text{Tr}(J_0) = 0$ and $\text{Det}(J_0) > 0$. From Equation (12), the appearance of Hopf bifurcation requires $\mu_2 > \eta$, and the steady state is

$$u^* = \hat{u}^* = \sqrt{\frac{(\mu_2 - \eta)(\rho_0 + 1)}{\kappa(\mu_2 + \eta)}}. \quad (15)$$

Since the steady state of the system satisfies Equation (9), we can derive a parameter condition where the system undergoes a Hopf bifurcation.

Theorem 2. *If the Hopf bifurcation occurs in the modified Fowler model at the fixed point (\hat{u}^*, \hat{v}^*) , then the parameters satisfy the formula that*

$$h_0 = \hat{h}_0 = \frac{\rho}{2\mu_2^2(\rho_0 + 1)} \sqrt{\frac{(\rho_0 + 1)(\mu_2 - \eta)(\eta + \mu_2)}{\kappa}} - \frac{1}{\eta} \left(\sigma + \frac{\rho(\rho_0 + 1)(\mu_2 - \eta)}{\kappa(\rho_0(\mu_2 - \eta) + 2\mu_2)} \right). \quad (16)$$

Derived from Equation (9), Equation (16) enforces $\text{Tr}(J_0) = 0$. However, the occurrence of a Hopf bifurcation additionally requires that $\text{Det}(J_0) > 0$, $\Delta = \text{Tr}(J_0)^2 - 4 \text{Det}(J_0) < 0$, and $\frac{\partial}{\partial h_0} \text{Tr}(J_0) \neq 0$.

The derivative of $\text{Tr}(J_0)$ in terms of h_0 cannot be computed directly, since $\text{Tr}(J_0)$ depends implicitly on u^* , which satisfies Equation (9). To determine whether $\frac{\partial}{\partial h_0} \text{Tr}(J_0) \neq 0$, we analyze how changes in h_0 influence the steady state u^* .

Corollary 1. *In the non-linear dynamical system corresponding to the modified Fowler model without diffusion terms, the condition $\frac{\partial}{\partial h_0} \text{Tr}(J_0) \neq 0$ is equivalent to the condition $\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}(u^*, h_0) \neq 0$, ensuring the transversality condition for a Hopf bifurcation.*

Proof. From Equation (9), we extend the function f to $f_1(x, y)$, s.t. $f_1(u^*, h_0) = f(u^*) = 0$. The function f_1 is defined as

$$f_1(x, y) = \frac{\mu_2}{x} \left(\frac{1}{\eta} \left(\sigma + \rho \cdot \frac{x^2}{1 + \kappa x^2} \right) + y \right) \cdot (1 + \kappa x^2 + \rho_0) - \rho = 0. \quad (17)$$

Then f_1 is continuously differentiable in the neighborhood of (u^*, h_0) and $\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x}(u^*, h_0) \neq 0$. According to the implicit function theorem (IFT) [12], there exists a continuously differentiable function $u^*(h_0)$ s.t. $f_1(u^*(h_0), h_0) = 0$. Then it can be derived that

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial h_0} \text{Tr}(J_0) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial u^*} \text{Tr}(J_0) \frac{\partial f_1(u^*, h_0)/\partial y}{\partial f_1(u^*, h_0)/\partial x}. \quad (18)$$

Since $\frac{\partial}{\partial u^*} \text{Tr}(J_0) \neq 0$, the condition $\frac{\partial}{\partial h_0} \text{Tr}(J_0) \neq 0$ holds if and only if $\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}(u^*, h_0) \neq 0$. \square

From Theorem 2 and Corollary 1, the remaining conditions for the existence of a Hopf bifurcation in the modified Fowler model can be derived.

Theorem 3. Suppose the steady state of the reaction system satisfies Equation (15), parameters fulfill the condition in Equation (16) and $\mu_2 > \eta$. A Hopf bifurcation arises if the following criteria are met:

(i) The Jacobian determinant $\text{Det}(J_0) > 0$ at the steady state is positive, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sqrt{\frac{-(\eta^2 - \mu_2^2)(1 + \rho_0)}{\kappa}} (\eta\rho_0 - \mu_2(2 + \rho_0))^2 \left(-4\mu_2^5(1 + \rho_0)^2 + \eta^4\rho_0^2\sqrt{\kappa(-\eta^2 + \mu_2^2)(1 + \rho_0)} \right. \\ & \left. - 2\eta^3\mu_2\rho_0\sqrt{\kappa(-\eta^2 + \mu_2^2)(1 + \rho_0)(2 + \rho_0)^2} + \eta^2\mu_2^2 \left(4\mu_2(1 + \rho_0)^2 + \sqrt{\kappa(-\eta^2 + \mu_2^2)(1 + \rho_0)(2 + \rho_0)^2} \right) \right) < 0. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

(ii) The eigenvalues are complex when the discriminant is negative, requiring $\Delta = \text{Tr}(J_0)^2 - 4\text{Det}(J_0) < 0$, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\mu_2 \left(\frac{2(\rho_0 + 1)(\eta + \mu_2)}{2\mu_2(\rho_0 + 1)} - 1 \right) - \eta \right)^2 - 4 \left[\frac{2\mu_2^3\rho(\rho_0 + 1)^2(\mu_2 - \eta)(\eta + \mu_2)}{\kappa\rho(\eta + \mu_2 + (\rho_0 + 1)(\mu_2 - \eta))^2\sqrt{\frac{(\rho_0 + 1)(\mu_2 - \eta)(\eta + \mu_2)}{\kappa}}} \right. \\ & \left. - \eta\mu_2 \left(\frac{2(\rho_0 + 1)(\eta + \mu_2)}{2\mu_2(\rho_0 + 1)} - 1 \right) \right] < 0. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

(iii) The derivative of the trace $\frac{\partial}{\partial h_0} \text{Tr}(J_0) \neq 0$ is non-zero, which is equivalent to $\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}(u^*, h_0) \neq 0$, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} & -4\mu_2^5(1 + \rho_0)^2 + \eta^4\rho_0^2\sqrt{\kappa(-\eta^2 + \mu_2^2)(1 + \rho_0)} - 2\eta^3\mu_2\rho_0\sqrt{\kappa(-\eta^2 + \mu_2^2)(1 + \rho_0)(2 + \rho_0)} \\ & + \eta^2\mu_2^2 \left(4\mu_2(1 + \rho_0)^2 + \sqrt{\kappa(-\eta^2 + \mu_2^2)(1 + \rho_0)(2 + \rho_0)^2} \right) \neq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

To rigorously observe a Hopf bifurcation in the system, the criteria in Theorems 2 and 3 must be strictly satisfied. We consider the range defined by $h_{\min} = \hat{h}_0 - \epsilon_1$ and $h_{\max} = \hat{h}_0 + \epsilon_2$ where $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2 > 0$. Within the parameter range, a Hopf bifurcation might occur in the system. However, for certain values h_0 , Equation (9) might admit no real solutions, indicating no fixed point in the system. In such cases, the conditions for the Hopf bifurcation are not well defined. The existence of ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 is verified in Corollary 2.

Corollary 2. In this system, there exist $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2 > 0$ such that a Hopf bifurcation is observed when $h_0 \in (h_{\min}, h_{\max})$ where $h_{\min} = \hat{h}_0 - \epsilon_1$ and $h_{\max} = \hat{h}_0 + \epsilon_2$. Note that \hat{h}_0 is defined in Equation (16).

Proof. From Equation (17), it is equivalent to show that $\forall h_0 \in (h_{\min}, h_{\max}), \exists u^* > 0$ such that $f_1(u^*, h_0) = 0$. According to Corollary 1 and the implicit function theorem (IFT), there exists a unique function such that $g(\hat{h}_0) = \hat{u}^*$ and $f_1(g(h_0), h_0) = 0$ in the neighborhood of (\hat{u}_0, \hat{h}_0) . \square

From Figures 2 and 3, we vary the parameter h_0 within a small neighborhood of the critical value \hat{h}_0 , where $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_2 = 0.0001$ are employed to see different behaviors. When $h_0 < \hat{h}_0$, the fixed point is a stable spiral; when $h_0 > \hat{h}_0$, the fixed point is an unstable spiral and a stable limit cycle emerges. The behaviors of trajectories indicate the occurrence of a supercritical Hopf bifurcation.

(a) Stable fixed point when $h_0 = \hat{h}_0 - 0.0001$.

(b) Distance to fixed point in different trajectories.

Figure 2: Hopf bifurcation observation when $h_0 = \hat{h}_0 - 0.0001$. Parameters: $\mu_2 = 0.02$, $\eta = 0.0155$, $\sigma = 0.001$, $\rho = 0.2$, $\rho_0 = 0.1$, $\kappa = 0.2847$, and $h_0 = 0.1$, with time step $\Delta t = 0.01$

(a) Unstable fixed point and stable limit cycle when $h_0 = \hat{h}_0 + 0.0001$.

(b) Distance to fixed point in different trajectories.

Figure 3: Hopf bifurcation observation when $h_0 = \hat{h}_0 + 0.0001$. Parameters: $\mu_2 = 0.02$, $\eta = 0.0155$, $\sigma = 0.001$, $\rho = 0.2$, $\rho_0 = 0.1$, $\kappa = 0.2847$, and $h_0 = 0.1$, with time step $\Delta t = 0.01$.

3 Finite Element Formulation

To determine the numerical solutions of the activator-inhibitor system, the finite element method (FEM) is employed. The variational formulation is used to derive the weak form by multiplying each equation with a test function, as shown in Equations (23) and (24). Then the spatial domain is discretized using triangular meshes, as displayed in Figure 4. The system of partial differential equations (PDEs) is posed as an initial boundary value problem (IBVP), where the initial condition is prescribed at time $t = 0$. To ensure biological significance, we assume that no biochemical instances flow across the domain boundary. Since the system is constrained to the seashell surface, we adopt the Neumann boundary condition in terms of the outward normal vector n , as commonly applied in pattern formulation and reaction-diffusion models [9, 20, 19]:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial n} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial n} = 0, \text{ on } \partial\Omega. \quad (22)$$

Among the two systems, the modified Fowler model extends the Gierer-Meinhardt (GM) system by incorporating additional parameters. Therefore, we derive the numerical methods for the modified

Fowler model, which simplifies to the GM model when certain parameters vanish.

3.1 Variational Formulation and Time Discretization

To consider the variational formulation of the modified Fowler model, we multiply each PDE with a test function and integrate both sides over the domain. After using Green's 1st identity, the zero-flux conditions are leveraged to derive the weak form, where the boundary terms vanish due to homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions [16]:

$$\int_{\Omega} \partial_t u \phi \, dx + D_u \int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla \phi \, dx = \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\rho u^2}{(v + h_0)(1 + \kappa u^2 + \rho_0)} - \mu_2 u \right) \phi \, dx, \quad (23)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} \partial_t v \psi \, dx + D_v \int_{\Omega} \nabla v \cdot \nabla \psi \, dx = \int_{\Omega} \left(\sigma + \frac{\rho u^2}{1 + \kappa u^2} - \eta v \right) \psi \, dx. \quad (24)$$

The test functions ϕ and ψ belong to the Sobolev space $H^1(\Omega)$ [5, 16], suggesting that the first derivatives of ϕ and ψ are square integrable. The use of test functions enables the extraction of residual dynamics of the weak form. Since the test functions are defined on the same Sobolev space, we leverage the same basis $\{\varphi_i(x, y)\}_{i=1}^m$ for the finite element subspace $V_h \subset H^1(\Omega)$ [13]. Functions $u(x, y, t)$ and $v(x, y, t)$ can be approximated in the finite element space [16, 24]:

$$u_h(x, y, t) = \sum_{i=1}^m U_i(t) \varphi_i(x, y), \quad v_h(x, y, t) = \sum_{i=1}^m V_i(t) \varphi_i(x, y). \quad (25)$$

Several authors apply Galerkin finite element formulations to reaction-diffusion models [1, 14]. By enforcing the variational form on the basis function $\varphi_j \in V_h$, the corresponding finite element equations in the vector form can be derived as

$$M \frac{dU}{dt} + D_u K U = F(U, V), \quad (26)$$

$$M \frac{dV}{dt} + D_v K V = G(U, V), \quad (27)$$

where we define the mass matrix M , the stiffness matrix F and non-linear vectors $F(U, V)$ and $G(U, V)$. The mass matrix M captures the inner product of finite element basis; the stiffness matrix F corresponds to the diffusion term using the gradients of basis functions; the non-linear vectors $F(U, V)$ and $G(U, V)$ are derived from the reaction terms of the modified Fowler model, approximated by u_h and v_h .

$$M_{ij} = \int_{\Omega} \varphi_i \varphi_j \, dx, \quad K_{ij} = \int_{\Omega} \nabla \varphi_i \cdot \nabla \varphi_j \, dx, \quad (28)$$

$$F_j(U, V) = \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\rho u_h^2}{(v_h + h_0)(1 + \kappa u_h^2 + \rho_0)} - \mu_2 u_h \right) \varphi_j \, dx, \quad (29)$$

$$G_j(U, V) = \int_{\Omega} \left(\sigma + \frac{\rho u_h^2}{1 + \kappa u_h^2} - \eta v_h \right) \varphi_j \, dx. \quad (30)$$

The above ODE systems involve the first-order temporal derivatives and non-linear interactions between variables. To further solve this equation numerically, authors use a time discretization scheme [27]. Despite the computational simplification, the forward Euler method requires extremely

small time steps to ensure stability due to the stiffness of the system. The backward Euler method is adopted to support stable simulations over larger time intervals [8].

$$M \frac{U^{n+1} - U^n}{\Delta t} + D_u K U^{n+1} = F(U^{n+1}, V^{n+1}), \quad (31)$$

$$M \frac{V^{n+1} - V^n}{\Delta t} + D_v K V^{n+1} = G(U^{n+1}, V^{n+1}). \quad (32)$$

Suppose that $u_h(x, y, t_n)$ can be approximated by $\sum_{i=1}^m U_i^n \varphi_i(x, y)$ at time $t = t_n$, then U^n represents the coefficients of the basis functions, similar to V^n .

$$U^n = [U_1^n, U_2^n, \dots, U_m^n]^T, \quad V^n = [V_1^n, V_2^n, \dots, V_m^n]^T. \quad (33)$$

We assume $A_u = M + \Delta t D_u K$, $A_v = M + \Delta t D_v K$, $b_u = M U^n$ and $b_v = M V^n$. To facilitate efficient computation, the authors leverage the semi-implicit scheme, where the nonlinear reaction terms are evaluated at the current time step [18].

$$A_u U^{n+1} = b_u + \Delta t F(U^n, V^n), \quad (34)$$

$$A_v V^{n+1} = b_v + \Delta t G(U^n, V^n). \quad (35)$$

Overall, the variational formulation converts the activator-inhibitor system into a weak formulation with test functions in $H^1(\Omega)$. The solutions are expressed by the finite element basis functions that define the subspace of Sobolev space. Spatial discretization using the basis leads to a system of coupled vector ODE equations. We adopt the semi-implicit scheme to treat the diffusion term implicitly and the reaction term explicitly [17, 18]. The scheme maintains temporal stability and addresses the stiffness of the system. Alternatively, the method is interpreted as a backward Euler scheme combined with Picard linearization, where the non-linear algebraic system is approximated using Picard iterations by replacing $F(U^{n+1}, V^{n+1})$ and $G(U^{n+1}, V^{n+1})$ with $F(U^n, V^n)$ and $G(U^n, V^n)$, resolving the interaction system numerically.

3.2 Triangular Discretization

Figure 4: Triangular mesh discretization for the seashell boundary with 500, 2000, and 10,000 mesh points, providing spatial resolution for FEM simulations.

Since we are simulating the pigmentation patterns in seashells, the 2-dimensional shape of the

seashell surface is irregularly organized. We discretize the geometric surface using triangular meshes to apply the finite element formulation on the spatial domain [4, 22]. The edges of triangles correspond to specific finite element basis $\phi_i(x, y)$. Each triangle is required to enclose a non-empty interval, avoid overlap and prevent hanging nodes. One example of discretization for the seashell surface with 500, 2000, and 10000 nodes is shown in Figure 4.

3.3 Consistency and Stability Analysis

The consistency of the finite element discretization is verified by computing the truncation error with respect to time and space, respectively. We apply the backward Euler scheme for the temporal discretization and leverage Taylor's expansion; then it can be derived as

$$\frac{u(x, t_{n+1}) - u(x, t_n)}{\Delta t} = \partial_t u(x, t_n) + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \partial_{tt} u(x, t_n) + O(\Delta t^2), \quad (36)$$

which shows that the temporal discretization is consistent of order $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t)$. For the spatial discretization of the weak form, according to [25], the truncation error satisfies $\|u - u_h\|_{H^1(\Omega)} = \mathcal{O}(\Delta x^2)$ under standard regularity assumptions. Thus, the method is first-order accurate in time and second-order accurate in space, i.e. $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t + \Delta x^2)$. Since we apply the Picard iterations after using the backward Euler scheme in time, the resulting stability region deviates from the fully implicit scheme due to the iterative linearization. Consider small perturbations close to the fixed point (u^*, v^*) , the finite element formulation can be written as

$$M \frac{U^{n+1} - U^n}{\Delta t} + D_u K U^{n+1} = a_{11}(U^n - U^*) + a_{12}(V^n - V^*), \quad (37)$$

$$M \frac{V^{n+1} - V^n}{\Delta t} + D_v K V^{n+1} = a_{21}(U^n - U^*) + a_{22}(V^n - V^*), \quad (38)$$

where $a_{11}, a_{12}, a_{21}, a_{22}$ denote the elements in the Jacobian matrix (10). We assume that $(\lambda_j, \hat{\phi}_j)$ are the eigenpairs for the system $M^{-1}K\hat{\phi}_j = \lambda_j\hat{\phi}_j$, where $j \in N^*$. Suppose the system has at least one fixed point (u^*, v^*) , and $W = [U^n - U^*, V^n - V^*]^T$ denotes the perturbation vector, which can be written as the projected form $W^n = \sum_j w_j^n \hat{\phi}_j$. Let $z_j = \lambda_j \Delta t$, then the update equation can be derived as

$$(I + z_j D) w_j^{n+1} = (I + \Delta t J_k) w_j^n. \quad (39)$$

Therefore, the amplification matrix is represented as $G(z_j) = (I + z_j D)^{-1}(I + \Delta t J_k)$, resulting in the stability characterization stated in Theorem 4.

Theorem 4. *Assume that the sufficient condition for a stable fixed point in Theorem 1 holds. The scheme is strongly stable if all the eigenvalues λ_j for the matrix $G(z_j)$ satisfy $|\lambda_j| \leq 1$ for all modes k , where the non-negative integer k determines the matrix J_k in Equation (10). The matrix $G(z_j)$ is written as*

$$G(z_j) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1 + \Delta t a_{11}}{1 + z_j d} & \frac{\Delta t a_{12}}{1 + z_j d} \\ \frac{\Delta t a_{21}}{1 + z_j} & \frac{1 + \Delta t a_{22}}{1 + z_j} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (40)$$

To ensure the validity of Theorem 4, it is noteworthy that the parameters in the modified Fowler model must satisfy the condition in Theorem 1.

3.4 Numerical Results

We evaluate the numerical solutions of the finite element formulation on the modified Fowler model. The FEM is implemented on the 2-dimensional seashell-shaped region with triangular discretization. The pattern formulation is initialized by introducing ridge perturbations radiating from the center of the seashell. The intensity of the patterns is evolved over time through the activator concentration in the modified Fowler model. The parameters of the modified Fowler model satisfy the linear stability condition in Theorem 1, ensuring the convergence near the fixed point. As displayed in Figure 5, the activator spreads and reorganizes through nonlinear interactions before time step 200. While at time step 1000, the pigmentation patterns become steady, indicating that the nonlinear system converges using the finite element formulation.

Figure 5: The 2D seashell pattern simulation at different time step using finite element formulation. Parameters: $D_u = 0.015$, $D_v = 0.0$, $\mu_2 = 10^{-6}$, $\eta = 0.014$, $\sigma = 10^{-4}$, $\rho = 0.1$, $\rho_0 = 0.1$, $\kappa = 0.1$, and $h_0 = 0.1$, with time step $\Delta t = 0.1$.

(a) Time evolution of spatial average and standard deviation.

(b) Log-log convergence of the average activator concentration over time.

Figure 6: Dynamical behavior of the activator-inhibitor system over time.

We analyze the dynamical behavior of the activator-inhibitor system by tracking the spatial patterns that evolved at each time step. Figure 6 (a) shows the spatial average and spatial deviation of the computed activator concentration in the surface region over time. The temporal evolution and subsequent saturation of the average activator concentration demonstrate that the system approaches a long-term equilibrium. The parameters in the activator-inhibitor system model satisfy the sufficient condition of a stable fixed point, which aligns with the steady behavior of spatial patterns as time evolves. The stability of the activator-inhibitor system is also observed in the spatial deviation over time, which decays gradually after reaching a peak. Since the system is linearly stable, it does not exhibit Hopf bifurcation or admit any limit cycles. To further analyze the convergence of the dynamical system, we examine the relative error of the spatial concentration over time using a log-log scale. We use the spatial pattern intensity at time step 3000 as the final state, and the convergence rate in terms of time steps is demonstrated in Figure 6 (b). The error decays slowly during the initial time steps and then decreases rapidly after a transient phase,

(a) Log-log convergence Plot for the finite element scheme with respect to time.

(b) Stability region for the finite element scheme without diffusion term.

Figure 7: Consistency and stability analysis.

reaching 10^{-3} . The behavior is consistent with the long-term convergence of the solution.

Then we assess the consistency and stability of the finite element discretization. To obtain numerical solutions, we apply the variational formulation by the weak form and discretize it in time using the implicit backward Euler scheme, then followed by the Picard iterations dealing with the nonlinear term. Based on consistency analysis, the scheme is first-order accurate in time and second-order accurate in space. However, in Figure 7 (a), the temporal convergence rate is approximately $O(\Delta t^{1.24})$, slightly above $O(\Delta t)$. The deviation in the order of accuracy contributes to the linearization using the Picard iteration. The approximation through fixed-point updates leads to additional errors in each time step, resulting in the deviation from the ideal order of accuracy. Since the activator-inhibitor system model with certain parameters admits at least one stable fixed point, which can be evaluated using the secant method, the stability region can be derived using Theorem 4. Here, we analyze the stability region by neglecting the diffusion term (i.e. $k = 0$) in Theorem 4. In Figure 7 (b), the scheme is not A-stable, as the stability region does not cover the entire left half of the complex plane. The limitation is due to the effect of Picard iterations, which alter the structure of the fully implicit scheme and introduce additional local error.

4 Parameter and Initial Condition Identification Using Physics-informed Neural Networks (PINN)

To simulate the spatial patterns of seashell surfaces, we leverage Physics-informed Neural Networks (PINN) to identify the parameters and initial conditions of the modified Fowler model [21]. The unknown parameters, including the diffusion parameters D_u , D_v and reaction parameters μ_2 , η , σ , ρ , ρ_0 , κ , h_0 , are treated as the trainable variables in the activator-inhibitor system model. Since the initial conditions of the modified Fowler model $u(x, y, 0)$ and $v(x, y, 0)$ constrain the system's behavior at the final step, the initial activator and inhibitor concentrations u^0, v^0 are also incorporated as part of the trainable variables. Given initial estimates, we use the finite element formulation to compute the spatial solutions at the prescribed final state. The parameters and

(a) Trained seashell patterns using PINN.

(b) Real seashell patterns.

Figure 8: Simulation results for parameter identification using PINN. Trained parameters: $D_u = 8.9874 \times 10^{-6}$, $D_v = 1.4880 \times 10^{-5}$, $\mu_2 = 1.7759 \times 10^{-6}$, $\eta = 0.0002$, $\sigma = 0.0001$, $\rho = 0.0666$, $\rho_0 = 0.0812$, $\kappa = 1.4409$, and $h_0 = 0.1$, with time step $\Delta t = 0.01$.

initial conditions are updated from the loss function and the process is repeated until the optimal configuration is attained. Applying the FEM in the modified Fowler model, the data loss and physics-informed loss are computed as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} = \sum_{i=1}^N (U_i^m - U_{\text{obs},i})^2, \quad \mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}} = \sum_{n=0}^{m-1} (\|\mathcal{R}_u^n\|^2 + \|\mathcal{R}_v^n\|^2), \quad (41)$$

where

$$\mathcal{R}_u^n = M \frac{U^{n+1} - U^n}{\Delta t} + D_u K U^{n+1} - F(U^n, V^n), \quad (42)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_v^n = M \frac{V^{n+1} - V^n}{\Delta t} + D_v K V^{n+1} - G(U^n, V^n). \quad (43)$$

Then the total objective can be computed by combining the data loss and physics-informed loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \lambda_{\text{phys}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}} + \lambda_{\text{data}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}. \quad (44)$$

The real seashell image is preprocessed into a form compatible with PINN training. We extract the boundary of the seashell surface and discretize it into triangular meshes for finite element formulation. We interpolate the intensity of the seashell surface onto the mesh nodes, simulating the spatial concentration of activator in the real seashell. In the forward pass of PINN, we use the finite element scheme to obtain the numerical results at a sufficiently large final time step. In the backward pass, gradients of the loss function in terms of the parameters and initial conditions are computed and the configuration is updated by minimizing the objective loss.

As displayed in Figures 8 and 9, the simulation result using the PINN model is demonstrated, where the real seashell image is treated as the ground truth. The training MSE loss for the simulation is 0.000253, demonstrating reasonable predictive performance in simulating the seashell

patterns. The finite element results based on the learned parameters and initial conditions effectively capture the seashell patterns, though certain regions in the trained pattern exhibit lighter intensities compared to the real data.

Figure 9: Training data loss and total loss in terms of number of iterations.

5 Codes Availability

The source code is publicly available at this [GitHub repository](#).

6 Conclusion

This work leverages the activator-inhibitor equations deriving from the biochemical interactions to simulate the seashell patterns. To extract the numerical solutions on the irregular seashell patterns, we develop the finite element scheme using variational formulation on the weak form, and time discretization with the semi-implicit scheme to approach the non-linear system.

We propose two theorems on the dynamical system and FEM. Theorem 1 is derived from the Turing instability analysis on the modified Fowler model, providing a sufficient condition on the parameters to ensure the existence of a stable fixed point. Although the fixed point does not admit a closed-form expression, the parameter condition indicates the existence and stability of a fixed point. The result is essential to analyze the convergence behavior of the dynamical system. Theorem 4 is established on Theorem 1, introducing an amplification matrix to determine the stability region of the finite element scheme. In addition, the analytical conditions for a Hopf bifurcation in the non-diffusive modified Fowler model are derived. By applying the parameters satisfying the threshold and inequalities, the system exhibits a supercritical Hopf bifurcation. We implement numerical simulations to capture the pigmentation patterns of seashells. With parameters satisfying the sufficient condition, the spatial patterns converge to a steady state and the stability region is displayed. For parameter and initial condition identification on the real seashell surface, we employ a PINN framework trained on the data loss and physics-informed loss, achieving reasonable predictive performance.

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